

THE SUBJECT, TASK AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF THE HISTORY OF PEDAGOGY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the subject, task and methodological basis of the history of pedagogy.*

Keywords: *history of pedagogy, methodology, task, education.*

ПРЕДМЕТ, ЗАДАЧА И МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОСНОВА ИСТОРИИ ПЕДАГОГИКИ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются предмет, задача и методологическая основа истории педагогики.*

Ключевые слова: *история педагогики, методология, задача, образование.*

All the peoples who lived in the land of Old Turkestan were able to revive and develop their national values due to independence. During the former Soviet regime, the achievements of the Uzbek people in the cultural, educational, social, spiritual, and educational spheres were belittled, and the idea that education and culture developed mainly in the West and later influenced the East was instilled. The merit of our independence is that the distortion of history has been put to an end. Our scientists have proven that the educational and cultural views of the peoples who lived in the land of Turan are higher than in the most ancient times. The peoples of Central Asia, which have a long and rich history, have created and improved their great heritage of education, educating hundreds of generations of humanity in the spirit of universal human qualities such as humanity, science, kindness, hard work, friendship, generosity, and the roots of the enlightening ideas created by our people go back to ancient times.

The Uzbek people have historically created their own unique philosophy in the field of education. Even during the period when Zoroastrianism was widespread in the lands where the current Uzbek people live, pedagogical ideology prevailed. This is reflected in some pages of the sacred book of the Zoroastrian religion, the Avesta, that have survived to us. However, the possibility of covering the history of education, science and culture of the pre-Islamic period is limited. Because, due to the looting and destruction carried out first by the Greek-Macedonian troops led by Alexander the Great, and then by the Arab conquerors led by Qutayba ibn Muslim,

almost all works and sources of that period were lost. However, the scientific study, thorough analysis and application of Islamic and post-Islamic pedagogical views, national educational traditions, values, and folk pedagogy is an important and urgent problem of today. Until we achieved independence, we based our educational work on European pedagogy and studied it. The current task is to focus on studying Eastern pedagogy and the most advanced traditions of Western pedagogy. Because science first developed in the East. The great German scientist Herler was right when he said: "The East is the teacher of Europe." The above ideas alone can serve as a basis for saying that culture and enlightenment spread from the East to Europe.

Because the emergence of literacy schools and ancient writings in the oldest sources indicates that the "Avesto", Sogdian, Bactrian, Urhun-Yenisei, Khorezm and other writings appeared on the land of Turon, and that the most ancient ancestors of the peoples living on this sacred land were literate people. Indeed, the cultural heritage of the Uzbek people is a vast sea.

There are such great forgotten discoveries in our past that our first task is to study them thoroughly and comprehensively. This requires bringing to the surface the valuable sources of our ancient rich educational heritage, our priceless treasure, and introducing it into the consumption of modern scientific and pedagogical thought.

During the 7th-12th centuries, culture and science in Central Asia developed incomparably.

In particular, interest in the exact sciences began to grow. In that historical period, such encyclopedic scholars as al-Khwarizmi, al-Farabi, al-Farghani, al-Beruni, Ibn Sina, az-Zamakhshari were born. Great thinkers played a key role in enriching the spiritual and intellectual world of man, in cultivating human consciousness, cultural and educational views, and created an unparalleled doctrine of human perfection. By the 15th - 16th centuries, ancient Turkestan brought to the world such scholars as Qazizoda Rumi, Ulugbek, Ali Kushchi, Alisher Navoi, Kamoliddin Behzod, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. At that time, a number of cultural and scientific centers emerged in the cities of Central Asia.

Thus, the peoples of Central Asia, in particular the Uzbek people, and their cultural and educational development have developed to an unprecedented extent over the centuries. In addition, his views on morality and pedagogy acquired a meaning and content that could be exemplary for the whole world. After the October Revolution, that is, starting in 1917, Soviet power began to be established in the Turkestan region "at lightning speed". This system promoted and incited communist ideology. In the early years of Soviet power, the tasks of opening new schools and strengthening them were set as a cross-cutting issue in Turkestan.

It paid attention to instilling the ideas of authoritarian power in the minds of young people and training teachers who would carry out these works. The direction and system of Russian public education took the lead in implementing these works. It is known from history that whichever state or country ruled, it tried to instill its ideology, culture, and moral beliefs in the subordinate country and people. Starting in 1924, the path to national culture gradually began to be blocked due to the disintegration of Turkestan and the establishment of national republics.

The writing system that had been used for centuries, in which encyclopedic sciences were written, was banned. First, a transition was made to a writing system based on Latin, then Russian graphics. This event deprived the peoples of Central Asia of the opportunity to study the history of their culture. In schools, the activities of individuals who had nothing to do with the development of the Uzbek people, not the founders of Uzbek science and culture, the great figures of the Muslim world, who made a worthy contribution to the development of world science, were taught. The study of the holy book of the Muslim world, the Holy Quran, and the hadiths of Muhammad (peace be upon him), was discouraged. As a result, the Uzbek people began to lose their national morals and traditions of upbringing. This loss had a negative impact on the development of Uzbek science, culture, and pedagogical sciences. By 1991, when the people of Uzbekistan gained independence, on the basis of its new national Encyclopedia, an opportunity arose to take a new approach to the Uzbek national science and culture, the “Theory and History of Pedagogy”, as in all other fields. In the past, prominent thinkers expressed important ideas about pedagogy, the study of which allows for the growth of pedagogical thinking and the increase of pedagogical culture. Based on the above ideas, we need to determine the goals and objectives of the theory and history of pedagogy that we want to study, and apply and improve it in connection with practice in the educational process.

So, the subject “Theory and History of Pedagogy” studies the development of education, schools and pedagogical theories in various historical periods, from ancient times to the present day, based on national and universal beliefs. After all, studying the history of pedagogy increases the pedagogical skills and culture of the teacher. It provides him with the opportunity to analyze the best practices of the past in connection with the educational process of modern schools. Studying this subject expands the teacher's level of general pedagogical knowledge and encourages him to have a correct attitude to the pedagogical heritage. It should be noted that by studying the history of pedagogy, we gain a general idea of the process of improving the system of world culture, education, and educational institutions.

The subject "Theory and History of Pedagogy" not only provides future teachers with knowledge, but also fosters in them a sense of national pride and honor. For example, as the head of our state noted, "The support of our people is the spiritual heritage left by our ancestors, which is a treasure in itself. This treasure must be used fairly."

The theory and history of pedagogy is a social science that approaches historical pedagogical phenomena based on the requirements of the era, reveals the diversity of the theory and practice of education at different stages. The theory and history of pedagogy is closely related to the following disciplines: pedagogy, psychology, history of culture, history of Uzbekistan, history of the peoples of the world, philosophy, ethnography, archeology, ethics and a number of other disciplines. We base our study and analysis of the theory and history of pedagogy on the following. These are: ancient writings, inscriptions, manuscripts, scientific and spiritual heritage of Eastern thinkers, folk oral literature, sacred books, pandnomas, programs, textbooks and textbooks, materials on issues of public education, press materials, works, speeches and articles on education of our Presidents Islam Karimov and Shavkat Mirziyoyev. The methodology of the theory and history of pedagogy is based on theories about national and universal values, folk pedagogy, the scientific and spiritual heritage of Central Asian and Eastern thinkers, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on education, and the idea of national independence.

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